

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

№4

ISSN: 2992-8982

<https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz/>

2025

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Bosh muharrir:

Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich

Elektron nashr. 1956 sahifa.

E'lon qilishga 2025-yil 7-aprelda ruxsat etildi.

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:

Karimov Norboy G'aniyevich

Muharrir:

Qurbonov Sherzod Ismatillayevich

Tahrir hay'ati:

Salimov Oqil Umrzoqovich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Abduraxmanov Kalandar Xodjayevich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Rae Kvon Chung, Janubiy Koreya, TDIU faxriy professori, "Nobel" mukofoti laureati
Osman Mesten, Turkiya parlamenti a'zosi, Turkiya – O'zbekiston do'stlik jamiyati rahbari
Axmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Kalonov Muxiddin Baxritdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Siddiqova Sadoqat G'afforovna, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Xudoyqulov Sadirdin Karimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Maxmudov Nosir, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Samadov Asqarjon Nishonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, professor
Slizovskiy Dimitriy Yegorovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Ikrom Akramovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abdug'aniyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xajiyev Baxtiyor Dushaboyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Hakimov Nazar Hakimovich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), professor
Ali Konak (Ali Ko'nak), iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor (Turkiya)
Cham Tat Huei, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD), professor (Malayziya)
Foziljonov Ibrohimjon Sotvoldixo'ja o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dots.
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, O'z.Respub. Bosh prokuraturasi boshqarma boshlig'i o'rinbosari
Ochilov Farkhod, O'zbekiston Respublikasi Bosh prokuraturasi IJQKD boshlig'i
Buzrukxonov Sarvarxon Munavvarxonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Axmedov Javohir Jamolovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), katta o'qituvchi
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), v.b. dots.
Djudi Smetana, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Krissi Lyuis, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Glazova Marina Viktorovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (Moskva)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD) (Turkiya)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhmatjon o'g'li, TDIU ITI departamenti rahbari
Ochilov Bobur Baxtiyor o'g'li, TDIU katta o'qituvchisi

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Editorial board:

Salimov Okil Umrzokovich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan

Abdurakhmanov Kalandar Khodjavevich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan

Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor

Rae Kwon Chung, South Korea, Honorary Professor at TSUE, Nobel Prize Laureate

Osman Mesten, Member of the Turkish Parliament, Head of the Turkey–Uzbekistan Friendship Society

Akhmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Akhmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Kalonov Mukhiddin Bakhridinovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Siddikova Sadokat Gafforovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogical Sciences

Khudoykulov Sadirdin Karimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Makhmudov Nosir, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Samadov Askarjon Nishonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Professor

Slizovskiy Dmitriy Yegorovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor

Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Akhmedov Ikrom Akramovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Eshtayev Alisher Abduganiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Khajiyev Bakhtiyor Dushaboyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Khakimov Nazar Khakimovich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor

Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Professor

Ali Konak, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor (Turkey)

Cham Tat Huei, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), Professor (Malaysia)

Foziljonov Ibrokhimjon Sotvoldikhoja ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor

Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, Deputy Head of Department, Prosecutor General's Office of Uzbekistan

Ochilov Farkhod, Head of DCEC, Prosecutor General's Office of Uzbekistan

Buzrukxonov Sarvarkhon Munavvarkhonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor

Akhmedov Javokhir Jamolovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences

Tokhirov Jaloliddin Ochil ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Technical Sciences, Senior Lecturer

Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Acting Associate Professor

Judi Smetana, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)

Chrissy Lewis, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)

Glazova Marina Victorovna, Doctor of Sciences in Economics (Moscow)

Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin kizi, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor

Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) (Turkey)

Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhmatjon ugli, Head of the Department of Scientific Research and Innovations, TSUE

Ochilov Bobur Bakhtiyor ugli, Senior lecturer at TSUI

Ekspertlar kengashi:

Berkinov Bazarbay, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Po'latov Baxtiyor Alimovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Aliyev Bekdavlal Aliyevich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Hakimov Ziyodulla Ahmadovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
G'afurov Doniyor Orifovich, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Tuxtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Xamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarim qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Yaxshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, katta o'qituvchi
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, mustaqil tadqiqotchi

Board of Experts:

Berkinov Bazarbay, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Pulatov Bakhtiyor Alimovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Aliyev Bekdavlal Aliyevich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Rustamov Ilkhomiddin, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Khakimov Ziyodulla Akhmadovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Kamilova Iroda Khusniddinovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics
Gafurov Doniyor Orifovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogy
Fayziyev Oybek Rakhimovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Tukhtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Khamidova Faridakhon Abdulkarimovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Yakhshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, Senior Lecturer
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, Independent Researcher

- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
- 08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti, O'zR Tabiat resurslari vazirligi, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi IJQK departamenti.

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot” jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi rayosatining 2023-yil 28-fevraldagi 333/5-sonli qarori bilan ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

MUNDARIJA

Цифровизация социально-трудовых отношений: вызовы и перспективы для работников	18
Абдумухтаров Анваржон Акрамжонович	
O'zbekistonda faoliyat ko'rsatayotgan soliq to'lovchi yuridik shaxslarning iqtisodiy faoliyatini rag'batlantirish masalalari.....	26
To'xtaboyev Nuriddin Isomiddin o'g'li	
Ecotourism in Protected Areas: A Literature Review.....	32
Ismoilova Maftuna Mamat qizi	
Iqtisodiyotning innovatsion rivojlanishi sharoitida xizmatlar sohasini rivojlantirishning hududiy xususiyatlari.....	38
Primova Shaxlo Jumayevna	
Statistik baholash va ekonometrik modellashtirish orqali biznes rivojlanish tendensiyalarini samaradorligini baholash.....	43
Xabibullayev Ibrohim, Saidova Marhabo Xabibullo qizi	
Tijorat banklarida xususiy kapital hisobi va auditini takomillashtirish	52
Qodirova Zilola Maxmud qizi	
Qo'shilgan qiymat solig'i ma'muriyatchiligining ilg'or xorij tajribasi.....	57
Erkayev Nodir Xudayberdiyevich	
O'zbekistonda yashil iqtisodiyotni joriy etish holati va asosiy yo'nalishlari.....	71
Madraximova Zulfiya Nurmatovna, Ishankulova Komila Kurbanovna, Ortiqboeva Aziza Xolmurza qizi, Omonkulova Ro'zigul Akmaljon qizi	
Challenges and opportunities in implementing green economy indicators in uzbekistan's industrial sector under the fourth industrial revolution.....	76
Shodmonov Ruslan Golib ugli, Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich	
Rivojlangan mamlakatlarga ishchi kuchi oqimi va O'zbekiston mehnat bozoridagi o'zgarishlar.....	89
Tilabova Kumush Farhod qizi	
Mamlakatda "yashil" iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirishning tashkiliy-iqtisodiy mexanizmlarini takomillashtirish	95
Yuldashboyev Azizulloh Bunyodbek o'g'li, Matkarimov Inomjon Baxtiyorovich	
"Ta'lim muassasalarida moliyaviy resurslarni samarali rejalashtirish va boshqarish"	101
Buyetdinov M.J., Medetbayeva D.T.	
Enhancing utilization and minimization of renewable energy systems in uzbekistan	105
Toyirova Hamida Umedovna	
Tijorat banklari daromadini oshirishda aholining savodxonligi va xulq atvorining roli	114
Shakhlo Davirova	
2020–2024-yillarda o'zbekistondagi iqtisodiy o'sish dinamikasi	120
Akbarov Nodir, Ibdullayev Navro'zbek	
O'zbekistonda xalqaro moliyaviy institutlarning yashil moliyalashtirish jarayonidagi roli va strategik yo'nalishlari	125
Gulmira Axmadjonova Xabibulla qizi	
Sug'urta tizimiga raqamli texnologiyalarning ta'siri	133
Uzaqova Kamola Bexzodovna, Yahyoyev Bahriddinxon Bahroil o'g'li	
Improving payment services practices in commercial banks: strategies for efficiency and security.....	138
Mamayusuf Abdusamatov	
Jahon moliya tizimi: asosiy tendensiyalar va rivojlanishning innovasion yo'nalishlari	143
Ataniyazov Jasurbek Xamidovich	
Повышение конкурентоспособности экологического туризма Узбекистана путём развития всесезонных горных туристических центров.....	150
Ахмедходжаев Равшан Темурович	
Xo'jalik yurituvchi subyektlar tashqi iqtisodiy faoliyatida valyuta operatsiyalarini takomillashtirish	157
Safarov Alisher Ibrohim o'g'li	

Oliy ta'lim tizimini miqdoriy va sifat ko'rsatkichlari asosida baholashning kompleks metodologiyasi.....	163
Hakimova Mushtariybonu Hamid qizi, Bozorova Muazzam Hamid qizi	
Ko'chmas mulkni boshqarish samaradorligini baholashning uslubiy yondashuvlari	167
Mirdjalilova Dildora Shuxratovna	
Xizmatlar sohasini rivojlantirishda kichik biznesning ahamiyati va uning innovatsion rivojlantirishdagi muhim xususiyatlari	173
Ulmasova Oygul Baxtiyorovna	
Результаты долгосрочного прогнозирования и стратегического анализа эффективной организации современного управления жилищным фондом.....	178
Бердиева Дилфуза Ахатовна	
Improving long-term assets accounting and auditing	184
Gulboy Yusupov	
Davlat budjeti va xususiy sektor ishtirokida oliy ta'limni moliyalashtirishning optimal modeli.....	189
Bozorov Alisher Ro'zimurodovich	
Xufyona iqtisodiyotni qisqartirishda soliq islohotlari va raqamli texnologiyalar: O'zbekiston tajribasi va xalqaro yondashuvlar.....	193
Choriev Makhmayokub, Karimov Mamurbek, Xamrayev Olimjon, Urazov Mansur	
Bank aksiyalarining bozordagi narx dinamikasi va unga ta'sir etuvchi omillar	200
Nomozov Samandar Shuxrat o'g'li	
Sanoatda rivojlanish kafolati: moliyaviy boshqaruvni raqamli transformatsiya orqali avtomatlashtirish.....	206
To'qliyev Abdirauf Bahodir o'g'li	
Inson kapitalini rivojlantirishning jamiyat farovonligi, aholi daromadlariga ta'siri.....	214
Bozorova Saxobat Abdujapparovna	
Анализ конкурентной среды: методология, примеры и этапы процесса.....	219
Садикова Раъно Абдуллаевна	
Tijorat banklarida muammoli kreditlarning nazariy asoslari va ular bilan ishlash mexanizmining zaruriyati	225
Salixova G.J	
Iqtisodiyotda energiya xavfsizligiga erishishning xorij tajribasi.....	230
Samandarov Og'abek Alisher o'g'li	
Measuring methodologies of influence of the esg factors	235
Tolipova Feruza Alisherovna	
Совершенствование налогового администрирования в условиях экологически устойчивого развития.....	240
Омонов Отажон Журакулович	
Moliyaviy vositalar asosida erkin iqtisodiy zonalarni rivojlantirish strategiyasini takomillashtirish	249
Quziev Ravshan Ramazanovich	
Методологические аспекты внедрения управленческого учета в университетах Узбекистана.....	253
Каршиева Мохинур Олим кизи	
Budjet tashkilotlarida tovar-moddiy zaxiralar hisobini takomillashtirish (tibbiyot muassasalari misolida)	257
Tulyaganov Abdumalik Abdiraximovich	
Умные города как фактор экономического развития.....	261
Нозима Кахрамоновна Хакбердиева	
Перспективы зеленого фактора экономического роста в Республики Узбекистан.....	266
Исламова Насиба Улугбек кизи, Абдурашидов Отабек Улугбекович, Мамасалиева Мукаддас Ибадуллаевна	
Qurilish korxonalarida sifat menejmentini joriy qilish mexanizmlarini takomillashtirish	270
Ergashev O'tkir, Saidov Mash'al Samadovich	
Xorazm viloyatida eksportni rivojlantirish uchun potensial imkoniyatlar va ularni baholash.....	275
Fozil Xolmurotov	
Maishiy xizmatlar sohasini davlat tomonidan tartibga solishning nazariy jihatlarini.....	282
Quliyev Begimqul Melikovich	

O'zbekiston hududlarida chakana kreditlashning o'sishi.....	289
Eshqobulova Charos O'roq qizi	
Empowering uzbekistan's grain enterprises: innovative strategies for sustainable growth and operational efficiency.....	292
Kurbanova Dildora Abdurakhmanovna	
Kapital investitsiyalarga doir axborotlarni xususiy kapital to'g'risidagi hisobotda aks ettirish uslubiyatini takomillashtirish	298
Boronov Bobur Farxodovich, Muxammadiev Zarrux Umarovich	
To'qimachilik korxonalarining yashil iqtisodiyotga o'tishi va yengil sanoat korxonalarini muqobil energiyadan samarali foydalanish yo'llari	303
Xolbekova Feruzaxon Rasulovna, Jalolova Aziza Jalol qizi	
Research on the effects of interest rate, inflation rate and gross domestic product (GDP) on the level of foreign direct investment (FDI) inflows (evidence from Uzbekistan).....	307
Azimov Shakhzod	
Organik mahsulotlar eksportini rag'batlantirishda maqsadli bozorlarga yo'naltirilgan marketing strategiyalari.....	314
Xidirov Shohrux Bobir o'g'li	
Korxonada iqtisodini barqarorligini ta'minlash masalalari.....	319
Abdullayev Maqsud Abdumaxmudovich	
Внедрение инновационных методов управления человеческих ресурсов в строительных компаниях.....	323
Джуроева Гузаль Шавкатовна	
Sug'urta zararlarini baholashda sun'iy intellektni qo'llash istiqbollari	328
Shoraximova Zilola Nasirdjonovna	
O'zbekiston Respublikasi mahalliy budjet tizimini moliyalashtirish masalalari	332
Qo'ldoshev Diyov O'rol o'g'li	
Raqamli texnologiyalar asosida raqamli ekotizimlar va ularning biznes-jarayonlarga ta'sirini aniqlashga ilmiy qarashlar tahlili	336
Suvanova Dilnoza Dilmurod qizi	
Innovatsion salohiyatni oshirish asosida qurilish materiallari sanoati korxonalarining boshqaruv mexanizmlarini takomillashtirish	342
Xaydarova E'zoza Shukurullayevna	
Aholi turmush darajasini dinamik kontekstli normallashtirish va moslashuvchan vaznlar usuli orqali baholash	352
Xolto'rayev Islom Ilhomovich, Ollokulova Feruza Mansurovna	
O'zbekiston Respublikasida xufiyona iqtisodiyotini qisqartirish va mamlakat rivojlanishiga uning ta'siri.....	358
Baxtiyov SHERALI Muzaffarovich	
Qayta tiklanuvchi energiya manbalari qurilmalarini aholi tomonidan xarid qilish va kompensatsiya ajratish jarayonlarini raqamlashtirish hamda tizimlar integratsiyasi istiqbollari.....	362
Ochilov Abdujabbor Akramovich	
O'zbekistonda kambag'allikni qisqartirish va aholi farovonligini oshirishda chet el tajribasining afzalliklari.....	369
Raxmatullayeva Shaxnoza Xamidovna, Akbarova Iroda Samatovna	
Qurilishda loyiha boshqaruvi konsepsiyasining mazmuni	375
Pulatov Shaxron Axmedovich	
Loyiha budjeti va uning ijrosini ta'minlash masalalari.....	379
Murodova Mohigul Chori qizi, Xamidov Odil Davurovich	
Qishloq xo'jaligidagi chorvachilik tarmog'ining iqtisodiy faoliyatini o'rta muddatli statistik prognozlarini tuzish (Andijon viloyati misolida).....	390
Iskandarov Davlatbek Xursanbekovich, Urishev Baxtiyor Abdusamatovich, Muydinov Xusniddin Nuriddin o'g'li	
Innovatsion faoliyatning iqtisodiy samaradorligini baholash va rivojlantirish yo'llari.....	397
Qurbanov Tolmasjon Namoz o'g'li, Shodiyev Fazliddin Qalandar o'g'li, Holmirzayeva Gulruh Akbarovna	
Fond bozorida kompaniyaning investitsion jozibadorligini baholash uslubi.....	403
Yulduz Usmanova	
Jahon bozoriga kirishda elektron bozorlarning ahamiyati.....	411
Hamroyeva Umida	

Comparative statistical analysis of foreign trade indicators of the Republic of Uzbekistan	415
Abdujalilova Bibisora Bakhodir kizi	
Yaxshi korporativ boshqaruv orqali aksiyadorlik jamiyatlarining kapital qiymatini oshirish: metodologik yondashuv.....	423
Urinov Bobur Nasilloevich	
JAS – barqaror qishloq xo‘jaligini rivojlantirishning yapon modeli vositasi	423
Baynazarov Elmurod Erkinovich	
Xususiy banklarning depozit operatsiyalarini mustahkamlash yo‘llari	435
Olimov Abror Axadjon o‘g‘li	
The impact of digital financial technologies on the financial system.....	439
Yahyoyev Bahriddinxon Bahroil o‘g‘li, Pardayev Olim Mamayunusovich	
Korxonalar eksport salohiyatini oshirishning “yashil” marketing mexanizmi	443
To‘rayev Shohrux Halimovich	
O‘zbekistonda ichki turizmni rivojlantirishda turistik oqim mavsumiyligini boshqarish yo‘llari	448
Fayazov Muxiddin Sobirovich	
Sanoat korxonalarida qayta tiklanuvchi energiya manbalaridan foydalanish bo‘yicha xalqaro tendensiyalar	453
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich	
Ayollar tadbirkorligining tarixi: O‘zbekiston va dunyo bo‘yicha rivojlanishi.....	459
Burxonova Sabo Tulanovna	
Qimmatli qog‘ozlar bozorida investorlar risklarini pasaytirishni takomillashtirish yo‘llari.....	466
Xalilov Umid Ishtemirovich	
Korxonalar moliyaviy ko‘rsatkichlari tahliliga fundamental yondashuv.....	470
Dilshodjon O‘rinov, Sanobar Ismoilova	
Iqtisodiy o‘zgarishlar davrida korxonalar moliyaviy barqarorligining ta‘minlanishi omil va mezonlari	475
Xolbekova Dilobarxon Rasuljon qizi	
Cash accounting as a tool of financial discipline and transparency in the public sector	481
Marqaboyev Sardorbek Abdusalomovich, Annayev Abdurasul Abdurashidovich	
Пути совершенствования практике финансирования социального предпринимательства.....	486
И.Ж.Исаков	
O‘zbekistonda an‘anaviy resurslar va qayta ishlanadigan energiya manbalarini rivojlantirish imkoniyatlaridan unumli foydalanish.....	490
Normurodov Xusan Eshmaxmatovich, Kaxramanova Sevda Shamsiddin qizi	
Ijtimoiy salohiyat – hududiy iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirishning boshqaruv obyekti sifatida.....	497
Erkayeva Gulbahor Panjiyevna, Zoirov G‘olibjon Toshtemir o‘g‘li	
Xorazm oziq-ovqat bozorida mahsulotlarning raqobatbardoshligini oshirishda marketing faoliyatlarini baholash usullari	503
Abdikarimova Zilola Bahramovna	
Переход к зелёной энергетике узбекистана как возможность достижения устойчивого экономического роста.....	508
Бай Жин Хуан (Bai Jin xuan)	
Изучение условий финансирования проектов международными банками развития	513
Жалилова Барнохон Суръатжоновна	
O‘zbekiston respublikasi budjet jarayonida budjetlarning ochiqligi va jamoatchilik ishtirokini oshirish.....	517
Shodmonqulov Temurbek Ulug‘bek o‘g‘li	
Chiqib ketayotgan aktivlarni hisobga olish va baholash masalalari	522
Kuziyeva Dinora Bahodirovna	
Asosiy kapitalga investitsiyalarning iqtisodiy o‘lishga ta‘siri.....	528
Qo‘shbaqov Aybek Shovqiyevich	
Changes in employee benefits and human resource management in accounting system of the Republic of Uzbekistan	535
Ravshanbekov Lazizbek Tolibjon o‘g‘li, Toshpulatova Munisabonu	

Iqtisodiyot tarmoqlarida suv iste'molini boshqaruvining raqamlashtirish tashkiliy-iqtisodiy mexanizmlarini takomillashtirish istiqbollari.....	541
Karimov Anvarjon Muqumjonovich	
Теоретические аспекты налогообложения доходов физических лиц на основе всеобщего декларирования	547
Усманова Мухлиса Сагдуллаевна	
Bank tizimini raqamlashtirish va uning bank barqarorligiga ta'siri.....	555
Sayfullayev Jamshidjon Xabibjanovich	
Kambag'allikni qisqartirish va aholi bandligini ta'minlashda tadbirkorlik faoliyatining o'rni.....	560
Saparov Ismat Chorshanbiyevich	
Innovatsion korxonalarda xarajatlar hisobining zamonaviy usullari	565
Turayev Og'abek Kaxramonovich, Ochilov Shavkat Toshmamatovich	
Дополнительные услуги в индустрии гостеприимства как эффективный инструмент продвижения бренда предприятия.....	570
А.И. Лесников, Д.В. Мамаева	
Преимущества и вызовы перехода на зелёную экономику.....	580
Умарова Гузал Гайратовна, Лапасова Камола Фарход кизи	
Yashil iqtisodiyot sharoitida hududlarda ishlab chiqarish korxonalarining iqtisodiy samaradorligini oshirish	586
Ibrogimov Sherzodbek Xalimjon o'g'li, Djurayeva Maxliyoxon Xayrullayevna	
Yashil iqtisodiy o'sishni ta'minlashda bevosita soliqlar rolini oshirish masalalari.....	591
Abdullayev Dilmurod Aliyar o'g'li	
The main directions for improving innovative activities in agriculture	598
Aytmuratova Miyrigul Zhalgasovna	
Klaster tizimi orqali O'zbekistonda qishloq xo'jaligining iqtisodiy o'sishi	605
Xaydarov Sardor Komil o'g'li	
Inklyuziv ta'lim: adolatli va teng jamiyat sari.....	610
Muxamedjanova Dilshodxon Muzaffarovna	
Yashil iqtisodiyot: muammo va yechimlar	615
Boymatov Xoliyor Qurbonovich	
Issues of using foreign loans in the development of the transport system in the Republic of Uzbekistan	621
Alimov Ilhomjon Ikromovich	
Проблемы и резервы развития пищевой промышленности в экспортном направлении.....	628
Ўролова Севара Бехзод кизи	
Оценка степени риска инновационной деятельности.....	634
Алиева Эльнара Аметовна	
Yashil innovatsiyalar, ularning turlari va omillari.....	638
Maxkamova Sayyora Shokirovna	
Qishloq xo'jaligida transport tizimidan samarali foydalanishning nazariy asoslari.....	641
Turdiyeva Irodaxon Ismoil qizi	
Soliq ma'murchiligida nazorat funksiyasi va unda kameral soliq tekshiruvi hamda takomillashtirish yo'llari.....	648
Hujamuradov Abrorbek Ro'zimurat o'g'li	
Sanoat korxonalarida xarajatlarni mahsulot tannarxiga taqsimlash metodologiyasini takomillashtirish istiqbollari	653
Safarov Javohir Ismoilovich	
Moliyaviy hisobotlarni shakllantirishda milliy standartlarni xalqaro standartlarga uyg'unlashtirish masalalari	659
G'aniyev Zafar Usanovich	
Ta'lim kreditini moliyalashtirish jamg'armasi faoliyati.....	666
Adilov Zuxriddin Marip o'g'li	
Tibbiyot muassasalarining moliyaviy ta'minoti va resurslardan foydalanish mexanizmlariga ta'sir qiluvchi omillar	670
Elmurodov G'ayratjon Abdumurodovich	
Tourism finance for sustainability: investing in green futures	674
Tashpulatov Sadriddin Sayfulloevich	

Ta'lim jarayonlarini boshqarishda mobil texnologiyalar	681
Esonova Mohiraxon Sodiqjon qizi, Ovхunov Iqboljon Abdunabiyevich, Sherzodbek Nabiyev Nurmuhammad o'g'li	
Banklarda risklarni nazorat qilishning amaliyoti	686
Jumanazarov Muzaffar Jumanazar o'g'li	
Налоговые реформы в Узбекистане: вызовы, достижения и перспективы	692
Садиков Искандар Гайратович, Буранова Лола Вахобовна	
Turizm xizmatlari samaradorligini baholash usullari va vositalari tahlili	704
Jiyanov Uktam Panjiyevich	
Korxonalar va tashkilotlarda xodimlarni boshqarish strategiyasi	712
Raxmonova Feruza Musakulovna	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkiloti direktorlarini menejerlik faoliyatiga tayyorlashning ahamiyati	716
Dusmaxamedov Abduljalil Abdusabirovich	
Davlat korxonasini xo'jalik jamiyatiga o'zgartirishning foydali jihatlari	720
Z.D. Sanjarov	
The role and main types of agricultural tourism in Uzbekistan	724
M.Xolmuratova, G.N.Tojiyeva	
Цифровые технологии как драйвер повышения эффективности банковского маркетинга	727
Кахрамонов Хуршидjon Шухрат угли, Маннабова Хулкар Фарход кизи	
Потребительская стоимость товаров в условиях экономики Узбекистана	735
Мусаева Шоира Азимовна	
Valyuta risklarini boshqarishda metching siyosatining ahamiyatini oshirish	739
Yaxuyayev Ziyodilla Lutfullayevich	
Yangi o'zbekiston iqtisodiyotida xususiy tadbirkorlikning roli va ahamiyati	744
Azimova Shoxista Salohiddinovna	
Improving the methodology for assessing the financial stability of banks	750
Sharipova N.H.	
Инструменты стратегического планирования и прогнозирования в управлении ООО "МТЕ ТЕХНИК": оценка и повышение финансовой стабильности	757
Нишоновна Муниса Одилжон кизи	
Актуальные вопросы налоговой политики	763
Бердыева Угулой Абдурахмоновна	
Ilm-fanni moliyalashtirish va innovatsiyalarni qo'llab-quvvatlash jamg'armasi	768
Ramazonov Javohir Bekzod o'g'li	
Jizzax viloyatida ekologik, rekreatsiya turizmlarini rivojlantirishning iqtisodiy samaradorligini baholash va uni prognozlashtirish	773
G'apparov Azim Qayumovich	
Qashqadaryo viloyatida ekologik va yashil texnologiyalarga kiritilayotgan investitsiyalar	781
Meylikov Fazliddin Abduhalim o'g'li, Buriyev Shaxbos Baxtiyorovich	
Biznes subyektlari auditida soddalashtirilgan moliyaviy hisobot tayyorlash usulini qo'llash xususiyatlari	786
Tajekeev Ziyatdin Kobeysonovich	
Biznes jarayonlarni modellashtirishning nazariy asoslari	791
Mullajonova (Matchanova) Shaxsanam Taxirovna	
Raqamli xizmatlar bozori: elektron tijorat orqali xizmat ko'rsatishning yangi bosqichlari	796
Maxammadaliyeva Muslimaxon Sherali Qizi	
"Yashil iqtisodiyot"ga o'tish zaruriyati va uni barqarorlashtirishning ahamiyati	800
Musurmankulova Gulchehra Isabekovna	
Ekologik turizm nuqtai nazaridan turizm marketingining usullari va asosiy vositalarining xususiyatlari	806
Yokubjonova Xulkarbonu Yokubovna	
O'zbekiston iqtisodiyotida turizmning o'rni va rivojlanish istiqbollari	815
Qosimova Fazilat, Kalandarov Ravshan	
Korporativ strategiyani ishlab chiqish bosqichlarining tahlili	819
Xidirova Marg'uba Rustamovna, Abduvasiyeva Marjona Anvarovna	

Mamlakatimiz turizmini rivojlantirishda investitsiyalarni jalb qilish bo'yicha o'tkazilayotgan islohotlarning o'rni.....	823
Ayubov Ilyos Ilxomovich, Nuridinov Bexruz Akbar o'g'li	
Hududlarda tadbirkorlarning islomiy investitsiyalardan foydalanish niyatlariga undovchi omillarning empirik tadqiqoti.....	829
Irgasheva Gulbahor	
Davlat vositalari yordamida innovatsion faoliyatni moliyaviy rag'batlantirish yo'nalishlari	836
Baxriddinov Nodirbek Zamirdinovich	
Важность качества управления на предприятиях общественного питания.....	842
Абдуллаева Зульфия Иззатовна, Махмудов Суннатжон Абдужаббор Угли	
O'zbekistonda "yashil" moliyalashtirishni rivojlantirish yo'nalishlari	848
Shaislamova Nargiza Qabilovna	
Mahalliy budjetning qo'shimcha daromadlarini shakllantirish yo'nalishlari.....	856
Yuldashev Javohirbek Ikromjon o'g'li	
Davlat moliyaviy nazoratida axborot texnologiyalaridan foydalanishni kengaytirish masalalari.....	860
Ro'zimatova Nigora Abdullaevna	
Принципы «справедливой стоимости» в мсфо: достоинства и проблемы применения в банках узбекистана	869
Айтмуродова Рушана Бахтиеровна	
Yashil iqtisodiyot loyihalarini moliyalashtirishning nazariy jihatlari	876
Allaberganova Asalxon Kadirovna	
Davlat moliyaviy nazoratini tashkil etish hamda amalga oshirish tartibini takomillashtirish	880
Xasanov Ruslan Raxmatovich	
Yirik soliq to'lovchilar va ularning investisiyaviy faolligini investisiyaviy chegirmalar orqali rag'batlantirish	883
Tohirov Shuhrat Niyoz o'g'li	
MHXS bo'yicha moliyaviy hisobot tayyorlashda foydalaniladigan tuzatuvchi buxgalteriya yozuvlar.....	888
Sheraliyev Xayrulla Karimovich	
Qurilish korxonalarida investitsiyalarni boshqarishning xorijiy tajribalari va ularni mamlakatimizda foydalanish yo'llari	894
Karimov Inomjon Ortikbaevich	
Davlat xaridini tashkil etishning ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy amaliyati va uni iqtisodiyotga ta'siri.....	900
Burxanov G'ofur Baxodirovich	
Влияние технологических инноваций на международные финансовые рынки, а также на финансовый рынок нашего государства.....	904
Бабаназарова Гульзар Зиуатдиновна	
Strategic development of global companies in modern conditions.....	909
Nasimov Bakhtiyor Vasiyevich	
Hududlarda sog'liqni saqlash tizimi asosiy ko'rsatkichlarini noaniq modellashtirish yordamida kompleks baholash.....	914
Ismoilova Dilfuza Ibodullayevna	
Tijorat banklari faoliyatini transformatsiyalashuv jarayonlarini takomillashtirish.....	923
Kulboyeva Nargiz Majitovna	
Сущность и причины возникновения проблемных кредитов.....	929
Улмасой Ахмедова Хусан кизи	
The use of digitalization and technologies in updating credit policy.....	934
Otabek Ma'mirjon ogli Azimov	
Финансовое моделирование сценариев развития предприятия с использованием методов многокритериального принятия решений (МКПР).....	938
Axmedov Akbarali Sultonmurodovich, Yuldosheva Gulnoza Abdinabievna	
Yuqori samarali energiya tejash texnologiyalari va katalizga asoslangan konversiya jarayonlari.....	945
Yusupov Ulug'bek Mamayusupovich	
Kambag'allikni kamaytirish maqsadida aholining ijtimoiy himoyalash mexanizmini takomillashtirish	951
Kasimova Gulyar Axmatovna	

Tijorat banklarida foiz riski muammosi	957
Turdiyev Abdulhakim Kulbazarovich	
Milliy mahsulotlarni tashqi bozorlarga olib chiqishdagi to'siqlarni bartaraf qilish choralari.....	964
Abdivaliyev Shahzodbek Xayrullayevich	
Kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlikni moliyalashtirish usullari.....	970
Kaxorova Zamira Safaraliyevna	
O'zbekistonda mehmonxonalarda ovqatlantirish xizmatlarini takomillashtirish konsepsiyasi: strategik yondashuv.....	974
Yaxshiyev Xusniddin Tolibovich	
O'zbekiston sanoatida "yashil texnologiyalar" dan foydalanish va barqaror rivojlanish.....	979
Ubaydullaeva Gulchehra Erkabaevna	
Sanoat korxonalarida resurslarini rejalashtirish (ERP) tizimlarini joriy etishning orqali iqtisodiy samaradorlikni ta'minlash yo'llari.....	985
Azizov Abdulla Abdissalamovich	
Yashil texnologiyalar asosida sanoatni modernizatsiya qilish	990
Muftaydinov Mansur Kiyomidinovich	
Ta'lim va ilm-fan rivoji – taraqqiyot garovi	995
Jamalova Gulnora Gulomovna	
Yashil iqtisodiyot sharoitida turizm sektorida barqaror bandlikni ta'minlash masalalari.....	1000
To'rabekov Sohijon Sherboy o'g'li	
Yashil energitikasi integratsiya qilish va energiya samaradorligini oshirishning zamonaviy usuli (aqli tarmoqlar-smart grids)	1007
Karimova Salima Elamonovna	
Yashil iqtisodiyotda tiklanadigan energiya manbalaridan foydalanish samaradorligi (TEM ko'rsatkichlar izohi)	1018
Sharifova Nargiza Djurayevna	
Экономическое образование молодёжи основа будущего страны.....	1023
Айматова Фарида, Айтиниязова Наргиза	
Biznes turizmining bugungi kundagi rivojlanish tendensiyasi.....	1028
Yangiyeva Sabrina Ixtiyorovna, Daniyarova Feruza Bahriddinovna	
Особенности кредитования сельскохозяйственных организаций и этапы его развития.....	1032
Ж.Я.Нуриллаев	
Xorijiy tajriba asosida O'zbekiston yashil iqtisodiyotini takomillashtirish yo'llari.....	1039
Xikmatova Husnora Fatxulla qizi	
Yashil iqtisodiyot sharoitida kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirishda davlatning roli	1045
Umarov Muzaffar Yusupbayevich, Otamurodov Rasulbek Batirovich, Xaitbayev Jasurbek Otaxanovich, Atadjanov Kadambay Sapayevich	
Mintaqada raqamli transformatsiya rivojlanishida moliyaviy texnologiyalarning ahamiyati.....	1052
Rustamov Jasurbek Ravshanbek o'g'li	
Tijorat banklaridan olingan kreditni qaytarishda foiz stavkalari ta'sirining tahlili.....	1058
Xanmuratov Roushenbek Xalmuxammetovich, Vaxabov.A.V	
Tabiiy va sun'iy tolalarning ekologik ta'siri va yashil ishlab chiqarish texnologiyalariga o'tish bosqichlari.....	1066
Raximov Furqat Jalalovich	
Maishiy kimyo tovarlari B2B taqsimotida chakana savdo tarmoqlari bilan marketing asosidagi strategik hamkorlik	1071
Ro'ziyeva Farzona Komiljon qizi	
Мировой финансовый кризис и его влияния на состояние экономики Узбекистана	1076
Раупова Мхлисахон Ибрахимжон кизи	
Uzoq muddatli aktivlar hisobini xalqaro standartlar asosida takomillashtirish.....	1087
Hakimov Faxritdin Abdusattorovich	
O'zbekistonda tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari	1093
Djo'rayeva Lola Abdugabbarovna	
Yo'l qurilish tashkilotlarida yo'l qurilish ko'lamini oshirib, samarali resurslar taqsimotini ishlab chiqish.....	1099
Raximov Dilshodjon Turdiali o'g'li	

Ilg'or xorij tajribalaridan O'zbekiston amaliyotida foydalanish imkoniyatlari	1104
Karimova Komila Daniyarovna	
Ichki audit samaradorligini tahlil qilish metodologiyasi.....	1111
I.G'.Isroilov	
Выведение практического сотрудничества на качественно новый уровень государств центрально-азиатского региона в укреплении концепции «зеленой экономики» в эпоху глобализации.....	1117
Парпиева Наргиза Тахировна	
Kimyo sanoati korxonalarida lean production konsepsiyasidan foydalanish istiqbollari	1122
Gulbayeva Feruza Islomovna	
Qimmatli qog'ozlar bozorida auditorlik xizmatlarining ahamiyati.....	1127
Maxmudov Saidjamol Kadirjanovich	
Tijorat banklari resurs bazasini mustahkamlash yo'llari.....	1131
Allaberganov Sirojali Saxatovich	
Теоретические основы формирования понятия «финансовая стабильность» Часть II.....	1143
Алиева Сусанна Сейрановна	
O'zbekiston moliya tizimini raqamlashtirishning rivojlanish tendensiyalari.....	1148
Tashmatova Rano Gaibovna, Qodirov Nurhayot Normuhammad o'g'li	
Theoretical basis of the use of modern information technologies in accounting.....	1154
Annayev Abdurasul Abdurashidovich, Tojiboyev Jasurbek Shavkat o'g'li, Rustamov Suxrob Asror o'g'li	
Moliyaviy bozorlar chayqalmoqda: investorlar uchun yangi signalmi?	1158
Xushvaqov Islombek Muxammadi o'g'li, Yaxshiboyev Jahongir Abdulimovich	
Yashil moliyalashtirish va esg samaradorligining iqtisodiyot barqarorligidagi o'rni.....	1166
Yusupov Sherzodbek Baxtiyor o'g'li, Atadjanov Kadambay Sapayevich, Madraimov Xabibulla Madaminovich	
Tijorat banklarida muammoli kreditlarni kamaytirish bo'yicha tizimlarni takomillashtirish yo'llari	1170
Bekmurodova Mahbuba Mahmudovna	
Maqola: Globalizatsiyada inson resurslarini boshqarishda raqamli transformatsiyaning rejasini tuzish	1177
Salimjonova Gulhayo Asliddin qizi, Ovxunov Iqboljon Abdunabiyevich, Nabiyev Sherzodbek Nurmuhammad o'g'li	
Turizm sanoatida Internet-marketing vositalari va ulardan samarali foydalanish	1182
Babaev Jo'rabek	
Ishlab chiqarishni boshqarishda mahsulot tannarxini kalkulyatsiya qilishning ahamiyati.....	1190
Asqarova Lobarxon Usmanjanovna	
O'zbekistonda ichki turizm faoliyatini rivojlantirishda transport infratuzilmasini boshqarishning tashkiliy-iqtisodiy jihatlari	1194
Turovov Maqsudjon	
Kichik biznes faoliyatini rivojlantirishda soliq siyosatini takomillashtirishning ahamiyati	1199
Abdurahmonov Abdumalik Abdug'ani o'g'li	
Madaniy-tomosha xizmatlarining tahlili va uni rivojlantirish yo'llari	1204
Annayev Abdurasul Abdurashidovich	
Цифровизация экономики и генезис стран мирового хозяйства	1211
Камилова Наргиза Абдукажоровна	
“Oila va xotin-qizlarni qo'llab-quvvatlash jamg'armasi” faoliyati.....	1216
Xushmurodov Baxtiyor Turg'un o'g'li	
Soliq stavkalarini tabaqalashtirish asosida soliq to'lovchilar iqtisodiy faoliyatini tartibga solish mexanizmlari.....	1220
Abduraimova Nigora Abdugapparovna	
O'zbekistonda yashil iqtisodiyotga o'tish va barqaror rivojlanishga ta'sir etuvchi omillar	1223
Xamdamov Shoh-Jahon Rahmat o'g'li	
Mintaqaning eksport salohiyati tahlili asosida istiqbolli y'nalishlarni aniqlash (Xorazm viloyati misolida).....	1229
Ibadullayev Ergash Bakturdiyevich	
Uy-joy kommunal xo'jaligini mintaqada innovatsion rivojlantirishni boshqaruvi.....	1235
Adilova Yulduz Shavkatovna	

Bank tizimi likvidligini ta'minlash vositalari va usullarini takomillashtirish	1239
Poyonov Bobir Bekturod o'g'li	
Milliy brendlarni shakllantirish orqali tashqi bozorlarda raqobatbardoshlikni oshirish	1245
Muratbaeva Eleonora Muxamedjan qizi	
Charm mahsulotlaridan tayyorlangan bolalar transformatsion sumka ishlab chiqarish iqtisodiy samaradorligi	1250
Ismailov Nurulla Tuychibayevich	
O'zbekistonda qurilish materiallari ishlab chiqaruvchi korxonalar faoliyati: iqtisodiy tahlil va islohotlar zarurati	1256
Raximov Ilyos Ikramovich	
Yoqilg'i-energetika kompleksida innovatsion salohiyatni oshirish strategiyasi.....	1262
Nabiyeva Saidaxon Abduvaxobovna	
Banklarda moliyaviy xavfsizlik kategoriyasining evolyusiyasi.....	1268
Qobilov Muhammad Ayubxon Yusufjon o'g'li	
Развитие системы бухгалтерского учёта и отчётности на современном этапе	1273
Мамажонов Акрамжон Тургунович, Юсупова Малика Ботиралиевна	
Практика банковского кредитования предпринимательских субъектов сферы услуг в германии	1279
Мукарова Сарвиноз Маликовна, Каримова Азиза Махомадризовна	
Статистический анализ теневой экономики в узбекистане	1283
Кошанов Абдимурат Азат ули, Абдиразакова Асемай Жандулла кизи	
The importance of using digital technologies in business	1288
Makhmudova Munisakhon Abbos qizi	
0,4 kv kuchlanishdan ta'minlanuvchi suv nasoslarini tarmoq faza kuchlanishi yo'qolishidan himoyalash	1292
Xalikova Xurshida Abdullayevna, Nurova Malika Abduzairovna, Mustayev Ruslan Aktamovich	
Tijorat banklarida korporativ boshqaruv tizimining samaradorligini oshirish	1297
Dexkonova Sayidaxon Nurmuxammadovna	
Ijtimoiy-iqtisodiyot va markaziy osiyo mamlakatlari ijtimoiy sohada	1302
Usmanxo'jayeva Surayyo Muxtarovna	
Aksiyalarni ommaviy joylashtirish amaliyotini tashkil etish va o'tkazish bosqichlari	1307
Raimov Farrux Avazjon o'g'li	
Approaches to effective management of tax liabilities through tax auditing	1311
Abdullayev Abror Bozarboevich	
Tijorat banklarida aktivlarni sekyuritizatsiyalash tizimini takomillashtirish.....	1316
Axmedov Akbarali Sultonmurodovich	
Tashqi va ichki omillar ta'sirini hisobga olgan holda korxonalar moliyaviy holati barqarorligining tahlili	1325
Eshkuvatov Azizjon Baxtiyorovich	
Tijorat banklari tomonidan ajratilayotgan kreditlarning iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirishdagi roli	1330
Masharipov Rasulbek Jo'rabekovich	
Sun'iy intellekt asosida bank tizimini modernizatsiya qilish va samaradorligini oshirish	1333
Boykulov Baxriddin Karshievich	
Aksiyadorlik jamiyatlarini moliyalashtirish manbalaridan samarali foydalanish.....	1338
Arifjanova Yayraxon Usmonxo'jayevna	
Ipoteka obligatsiyalarining mamlakat iqtisodiyotining o'sishidagi ahamiyati hamda mazkur obligatsiyalar bilan bog'liq risklar	1343
Ibrohimov Yorqinjon To'lqin o'g'li	
Анализ спроса и потребительского поведения на продукцию, выращенную гидропонным методом	1349
Дурманов Акмал Шаймарданович	
Global moliyaviy inqirozlar sharoitida aholi daromadlarining barqarorligini ta'minlash strategiyalari	1355
Qurbanov Ulug'bek Erkinovich, Nutfullayev Shohrux Mexli o'g'li	
“O'zbekistonning “yashil iqtisodiyot”ga o'tish strategiyasi: mavjud muammo va istiqbolli imkoniyatlar”	1359
Ismailov Dilshod Anvarjonovich, Akramova Aziza Abduvohidovna	

Aksiyadorlik jamiyatlarida davlat xaridlarini tashkil etish amaliyotini takomillashtirish.....	1366
Saidaxmedova Aida Mirzayevna	
O'zbekistonda ekologik turizmni rivojlantirish masalalari.....	1372
Abduraxmonova Ziyoda Abdullayevna	
Netto ish haqini hisoblashning innovatsion usullari.....	1378
Mirmahmudov Murod Irismatovich	
Xizmat ko'rsatish sohasida tadbirkorlik: iqtisodiy va ijtimoiy istiqbollar	1383
Kaydarova Shoxista Davranovna	
Texnologiya fanida sun'iy intellekt va kompyuter texnologiyalaridan foydalanish	1388
Ashurov Nazar Raxmatullaevich	
Korporativ xaridlarni amalga oshirishdagi byurokratik to'siqlar va ularni bartaraf etish usullari	1391
Qurbanov Shohboz Lutfillayevich	
Yashil yondashuvlar asosida barqaror iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirishning nazariy asoslari.....	1396
Ubaydullaev No'monjon Isroilovich	
Qishloq xo'jaligi mahsulotlarini SWOT va pestel tahlil qilish orqali iqtisodiy bashoratlash.....	1401
Karimova Maftuna Nurdinovna	
O'tkir revmatik isitmasi bor bolalarda kardiometriya ko'rsatkichlarining statistik tahlili	1407
Muxamadiyeva Lola Atamuradovna	
Ways to develop digital economy and electronic government in UZBEKISTAN	1418
Nuritdinova Dilshodaxon Abdulla kizi	
O'zbekistonda hayot sug'urtasining joriy etilishi va unga ta'sir etuvchi demografik omillar ta'siri.....	1422
Mirzamahmudova Madina Odiljon qizi	
Global iqlim o'zgarishining turizm sektoriga ta'siri: muvofiqlashtirish va barqarorlikka erishish strategiyalari	1428
Karimova Shaxnoza Uktamovna	
Prospects for the development of islamic microfinance services in uzbekistan.....	1433
Sadullaeva Gulnoza Usmanovna	
Global iqlim o'zgarishi riski uning mamlakat iqtisodiyoti moliyaviy sektoriga ta'siri	1439
Baratov Sa'dulla Norjigit o'g'li, Jo'rayev Behzod Nuraliyevich	
Перспективы унификации налогов на землю и имущество	1444
Акбарова Нилуфар Неъматжановна	
Banklarda xalqaro moliyaviy hisobot standartlari (IFRS) asosida hisobot tuzish tartibi	1449
Arziboyeva Ravzaxon Sattarovna	
Kichik biznes subyektlari iqtisodiy xavfsizligini ta'minlash mexanizmini takomillashtirish	1454
Akbarov Abdulhamid Akmal o'g'li	
O'zbekiston Respublikasi hududlarida demografik jarayonlarning dinamikasi tahlili	1458
Xamitova Mavluda Sindarovna	
Ta'minot zanjirlarini boshqarishda big datadan foydalanishni afzalliklari	1463
Yuldashev Abduhakim Abdukarimovich, Quryazov Quryozbek Ergash o'g'li	
Yashil texnologiyalardan keng foydalanish – yashil investitsiyalarning poydevori.....	1467
Xursandov Komiljon Maxmatkulovich	
Raqamli transformatsiya sharoitida tijorat banklarining strategik boshqaruv tizimini takomillashtirish yo'llari.....	1470
Umurov Jasurbek Jamil o'g'li	
Digital neighbourhood contexts in youth employment and competency frameworks	1474
Gulsara Ostonakulova	
Роль организации антимонопольной политики в национальной экономике в обеспечении экономической безопасности и конкурентоспособности.....	1482
Глазова Марина Викторовна	
Rivojlangan sug'urta bozorlarida investisiya faoliyati tahlili.....	1487
Suyunov Isomiddin Tilovkobilovich	
O'zbekiston respublikasida qurilish kompleksining hozirgi holati va asosiy rivojlanish tendensiyalari.....	1491
Muxibova Guli Yarkinovna	

Aholining turmush farovonligini oshirishda kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlikning roli	1496
Ostanova Nargiza Baratovna	
Tadbirkorlik faoliyatini boshqarishda rahbarlik uslubi: demokratik rahbarlar	1508
Amonov Mehridin Oromiddinovich	
Korxonlarni rivojlantirishda yashil iqtisodiyot mexanizmlarini joriy etish	1513
Yusupov Bekzod Ulugbekovich	
O'zbekistonda sog'lomlashtirish turizmi infratuzilmasini rivojlantirishni ko'p omilli ekonometrik modellashtirish asosida prognozlash	1517
Norchayev Asatullo Norbo'tayevich	
"Ijtimoiy himoya" kategoriyasiga qaratilgan nazariy qarashlar evolyusiyasi	1526
Bobonov N.H	
Majburiyatlar hisobini xalqaro standartlar asosida takomillashtirishning nazariy asoslari.....	1532
Ikromova Odinaxon	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida sanoat mahsulotlari ishlab chiqarish sifatini oshirishda raqamli xizmatlarning obyektiv zarurati	1537
Norov Murodjon Mahmudovich	
Oliy ta'lim xizmatlari mohiyati va rivojlanish nazariyasi.....	1541
Iskandarov Shahboz Shavkat o'g'li	
Davlat-xususiy sheriklikka oid ilmiy yondashuv va qarashlarning rivojlanish tendensiyalari	1545
O'ktamova Nargiza Narzulla qizi	
Theoretical foundations of time series analysis in green economy	1552
Muradov Rustamjon Sobitkhonovich	
Korxonalar faoliyati samaradorligini baholashning kompleks yondashuvi: nazariya va amaliyot.....	1563
Xalilov Bekzod Axmatovich	
Aholi real daromadlarini shakllantirishda inson kapitalini rivojlantirishning roli.....	1568
Iskandarova Dilafuz Ikrom qizi	
Yashil iqtisodiyotda transportning tutgan o'rnini.....	1573
Yuldasheva Saodat Arslanovna, Otanazarova Charos Baxtiyor qizi	
Xalqaro standartlar asosida hisob siyosati metodologiyasini takomillashtirish.....	1577
Qurbanboev Jurabek Eruvboevich	
Sanoat tarmoqlarini barqaror rivojlantirishda "yashil" iqtisodiyotdan samarali foydalanish istiqbollari.....	1585
Yuldasheva Saida Nematovna	
Mintaqaviy mehnat bozorini tartibga solishning tashkiliy-iqtisodiy mexanizmlari.....	1593
Azadova Gulnoza Sardorbekovna	
O'zbekistonda yashil sug'urta mahsulotlarini rivojlantirishda xorij tajribalari	1600
Yusufov Asfandiyor Eldor o'g'li	
Понятие и типы финансовых шоков: макроэкономический контекст и микроуровневые последствия	1606
Захарова Ирина Борисовна	
Современное состояние оздоровительного туризма в Узбекистане.....	1611
Сирлибеков Хабибулло Шакарбоевич	
Impact of industrial development on macroeconomic indicators.....	1621
Olchinboyev Otabek Abdusamad ugli	
Анализ предпочтений на рынке электронной торговли в Узбекистане	1625
Уразов Комил Бахрамович, Хушмуродова Мадина	
Методы оценки деятельности акционерных обществ с учетом инвестиционных рисков.....	1639
Айтмуратова Улбике Жалгасовна	
Xalqaro moliyaviy markazlar va ularning jahon iqtisodiyotidagi roli.....	1645
Sharipova Shaxinabonu Orif qizi	
Development of modern tourism industry in Uzbekistan through smart technologies and digital transformation.....	1649
Master's student at Silk Road University	
Iqtisodiyotda qiymat nazariyasi asosida qishloq xo'jaligida qo'shilgan qiymatni shakllanishi.....	1656
Azizov Shohsuvor Yuldashevich	

Xo'jalik yurituvchi subyektlar, ularda hisobdorlik va boshqaruvda axborotlarning tahliliyligini oshirish masalalari.....	1659
Yusupov Azizbek Baxtiyor o'g'li	
"Yashil" iqtisodiyotga o'tishda xalqaro hamkorlik: O'zbekistonning tashqi iqtisodiy faoliyatidagi yangi tendensiyalar	1665
Xashimov Pazliddin Zukurovich, Sobirxo'jaev Xadyatillo Billoxon o'g'li	
Uy-joy fondini boshqarishning mazmun-mohiyati va o'ziga xos xususiyatlari	1671
Inoyatova Durdona Shoxaydarovna	
O'zbekiston va markaziy osiyo davlatlari budget siyosatining qiyosiy tahlili.....	1677
Sharoxmatov Abduraxim Abdulamitovich	
Kambag'allikni qisqartirish – mamlakatda barqaror ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy o'sishni ta'minlash omili sifatida	1683
Tashbaeva Saodatxon Alisherovna	
Финансовые технологии: сущность и задачи.....	1687
Амонова Хафиза	
O'zbekistonning ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy rivojlanish holati va investitsiya jarayonlarining o'ziga xos xususiyatlari.....	1690
O'rinov Akmaljon Axmadjonovich	
Budget tashkilotlarida ichki audit tizimini shakllantirish: xorijiy tajriba.....	1695
Po'latov Tirkash Sotiboldiyevich	
"Ichki iste'mol uchun qayta ishlash" bojxona protseduralarini O'zbekiston sharoitida qo'llashning ahamiyati.....	1699
Buranov Husniddin Husenovich, Allabergenov Ozodjon Maksudbayevich	
To'qimachilik sanoatini rivojlantirishning tashkiliy-iqtisodiy mexanizmini takomillashtirish.....	1703
Muxiddinova Kamola Sagdullayevna	
O'zbekiston respublikasida qishloq xo'jaligi tarmog'ining rivojlanishini iqtisodiy tahlili	1708
Aysachev Abdulfotix Abdulfaizovich	
Kichik biznes korxonalari uchun eksport salohiyatini oshirish yo'llari va strategiyalar	1714
Mo'minova Kanizaxon	
Buxoro viloyatida agroklastar tizimi rivojlantirish yo'nalishlari va iqtisodiy samaradorligi	1718
Ro'ziyev Sobirjon Samatovich, Boltayeva Shaxnoz Bebudovna	
Temir yo'l tizimini modernizatsiya qilishda imitatsion model asosida tahliliy yondashuv.....	1724
Mamasidikov Muxsinjon Musajonovich	
Климатическая политика и «зеленая» трансформация: Торговля углеродными единицами (Углеродная торговля)	1730
Исламов Шохзод Шухрат ўғли	
O'zbekistonda kichik va o'rta biznes sohasining rivojlanish tendensiyalarini ekonometrik modellarini tuzish asosida baholash.....	1738
Arzikulov Otabek Ali o'g'li, Xudoyorova Ruhshona Toshpo'lot qizi	
Ikkilamchi bozorda noturar joy ko'chmas mulk qiymatini baholashning huquqiy mexanizmini takomillashtirish	1743
Fayziyeva Gulnoza Abdurahmonovna	
O'zbekiston da yashil iqtisodiyotni barqaror rivojlantirishning strategik yo'nalishlari	1749
Otaxonova Dinora Musaboy qizi	
Tibbiy xizmatlarning rivojlanish evolutsiyasi va samaradorlik hamda xarajatlari tushunchalarining mohiyati.....	1754
Axmedov Zafarjon A'zamovich, Karabayev Sanjar Abdusamatovich, Uraqov Shokir Ulashovich	
Kichik biznes korxonalarida sanoat ishlab chiqarish samaradorligiga ta'sir etuvchi omillar	1762
Axmedova Nilufar Shuxratovna, Amirov Zubaydulla Toir o'g'li	
Raqamli iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirish sharoitida yoshlarning ish bilan bandlik darajasini oshirish yo'llari	1768
Sharipov Sherzod Shavkatovich	
Paxta-to'qimachilik klasterlarida buxgalteriya hisobotlarini yuritishning muhim jihatlari	1772
Madartov Bahrom Quvondiqovich	
Aksiyadorlik jamiyatlarida o'z kapitali hisobini xalqaro moliyaviy hisobot standartlari asosida yuritishni takomillashtirish.....	1776
Axmedov Latayibxon Mamitxonovich	

Reklama xizmatlari bozorida raqobatbardoshlikni oshirish yo'llari.....	1780
Xamrakulov Azamat Baxritdinovich	
Iqtisodiyotni erkinlashtirish sharoitida xizmatlar sohasini rivojlantirish tendensiyalari.....	1785
Seytimbetov Kabul Serimbetovich	
O'zbekiston va islom taraqqiyot banki: hamkorlik va rivojlanish istiqbollari.....	1789
Dilovarxo'jayeva Dilnozaxon Shavkatxo'ja qizi	
Xodimlarni rag'batlantirish tizimida mehnatga haq to'lash	1793
Xamdamov Nuriddin Abdimalikovich	
Mahalliy budjet daromadlarini shakllantirishda soliqlarning tutgan o'rni	1797
Kimsanboyeva Maftuna Baxodirovna	
Dunyo mamlakatlarida xorijiy talabalar oqimi tahlili va ta'lim eksportining demografik salohiyati	1802
Abdullayev Javoxir Jaxongirovich	
Davlat qarzini boshqarish amaliyotini takomillashtirish	1809
Djurayev Paxlavonjon Usarovich	
Mintaqada chakana savdoni rivojlantirish istiqbollari.....	1815
Ismoilov Shohjahon O'tkir o'g'li, Abdullayev Ilyos Sultanovich	
Yuk tashish sohasini davlat tomonidan qo'llab-quvvatlash mexanizmini takomillashtirish	1819
Omarov Mamanbiy Allabergenovich	
Mathematical statistics in biology and medicine	1826
Vokhidov Alikul, Orazbaeva Ayjamal, Tog'amurotova Jasmina, Turotova Dildora	
“Yashil” energetika salohiyatini ro'yobga chiqarishda xatarlar va muammolar: O'zbekiston sharoitida tahlil va yechimlar	1833
Nasretdinov Nodir Tulqinovich	
Aglomeratsiyalar ekologik barqarorligi: koreya respublikasi tajribasi va o'zbekistonda uni qo'llash imkoniyatlari	1837
Shohruh Shuhrat o'g'li Mardonov	
Sanoat sohasida energiya samaradorligini oshirishning iqtisodiy va ekologik afzalliklari.....	1843
Iminov Farxodjon Tohirjonovich	
Современные принципы и дальнейшее совершенствование налогового администрирования в узбекистане.....	1848
Буранова Лола Вахобовна, Рахимова Шахло Ражапбоевна	
Роль малого и частного бизнеса в инновационном развитии экономики узбекистана: сравнительно-аналитический подход	1858
Мадраимова Согдиана Равильевна	
Sayyohlarning shikoyatlarini ko'rib chiqish va ularning huquqiy huquqlarini tiklash mexanizmlari	1864
Sayfiddinov Sharofiddinxo'ja Najmiddin o'g'li	
Sanoat korxonalarida inqozga qarshi boshqaruv mexanizmlarini takomillashtirish	1869
Muxammadov Umarjon Muxammad o'g'li	
Xalqaro kompaniyalarda Big Data va biznes jarayonlarini innovatsion boshqarish	1885
To'g'onov Ibrohimxo'ja, Mardiyev Bunyod Sirojiddin o'g'li	
Transport vositalari egalari fuqarolik javobgarligi sug'urtasini rivojlantirishning zamonaviy yo'nalishlari.....	1889
Darxanova Umida	
Tijorat banklarida moliyaviy injiniring konsepsiyasini mustahkamlashni takomillashtirish	1895
Saipnazarov Sherbek Shaylavbekovich	
O'zbekistonda aholi farovonligini ta'minlash yo'llari	1902
Ibragimov Elmurod Gulboynor o'g'li	
“Uzsuvta'minot” aj tizim tashkilotlarida biznes jarayonlari bo'yicha boshqaruv hisobini tashkil etish uchun hisob tizimining xususiyatlari.....	1906
Saidakbarov Xusniddin Abdusalomovich	
Ways to develop and stimulate innovative activity of the enterprise	1909
U. Yusupov, Ye Junjiye	
Трансформация мировой торговли: путь от протекционизма к свободному рынку на примере узбекистана.....	1914
Олимова Насиба Акмаловна, Камилова Наргиза Абдукахоровна	

Xalqaro tajribada mulkni qayta baholash metodlari: O'zbekiston uchun moslashtirish imkoniyatlari.....	1920
Xadjayev Kamoliddin Fazliddinovich	
O'zbekistonda professional futbol klublarini moliyalashtirish mexanizmini takomillashtirish	1924
Mirzayev Ulug'bek Abdusattarovich	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida tijorat banklarining xizmat turlarining huquqiy asoslari.....	1931
Umurzoqova Adiba Ochilovna	
Qurilish materiallari sanoatida ishlab chiqarishni tashkil etish va innovatsion rivojlanish tendensiyalari.....	1937
Haqberdiyev Ulug'bek Nasrullo o'g'li	
O'zbekiston Respublikasi tijorat banklarida biznes ekotizimini takomillashtirishning nazariy asoslari.....	1944
Shoymardonov Orziqul Jo'ra o'g'li	
The impact of intensive urbanization in tashkent on economic stability, environmental conditions, and demographic processes.....	1949
Khandamirdzhanova B.M., Shoislomova Komila Batyrovna	

THE IMPACT OF INTENSIVE URBANIZATION IN TASHKENT ON ECONOMIC STABILITY, ENVIRONMENTAL CONDITIONS, AND DEMOGRAPHIC PROCESSES

Khandamirdzhanova B.M.

UWED student

benazirhondamirova@gmail.com

Scientific supervisor:

Shoislomova Komila Batyrovna

Lecturer of the Department of World Economy

Annotatsiya: Urbanization is the backbone of economic development, but it can also lead to serious disaster in terms of its speedy and ungoverned character. The case study, focus on Tashkent, by describing the economic instability, environmental degradation, and demographic pressures caused by intensive urbanization, shows an example of “urban-affected economic and social issues”. It causes distortions in the housing market, increases the cost of living, destroys the environment and encourages unsustainable population growth in the capital. This study, using empirical data and case studies, illustrates the consequences of unrestrained urban growth. The insights are important for urban policy discourse as it helps acknowledge significant stressors, providing guidance for urban planning that is equitable and balanced, and even emphasizing safeguards for sustainable development, that are effective in managing resources and regulatory measures to avert prolonged crises over time.

Kalits o'zlar: urbanization, economic stability, environmental impact, demographic trends, real estate crisis, overconstruction, Uzbekistan.

Abstract: Urbanizatsiya iqtisodiy rivojlanishning asosiy omili hisoblanadi, biroq uning tezkor va nazoratsiz xarakteri jiddiy inqirozlarga olib kelishi mumkin. Toshkent misolida o'tkazilgan tadqiqot intensiv urbanizatsiya natijasida yuzaga keladigan iqtisodiy beqarorlik, ekologik degradatsiya va demografik bosimlarni tasvirlab, "shahar ta'siridagi iqtisodiy va ijtimoiy muammolar" misolini ko'rsatadi. Bu jarayon uy-joy bozorida buzilishlarga olib keladi, yashash narxini oshiradi, atrof-muhitni vayron qiladi va poytaxtda barqaror bo'lmagan aholi o'sishini rag'batlantiradi. Ushbu tadqiqot empirik ma'lumotlar va misol tahlillari yordamida nazoratsiz shahar rivojlanishining oqibatlarini yoritib beradi. Ushbu tushunchalar urbanizatsiya siyosatini muhokama qilish uchun muhim bo'lib, stress omillarini anglashga yordam beradi hamda resurslarni boshqarish va uzoq muddatli inqirozlarning oldini olish uchun samarali tartibga solish choralarini ta'kidlagan holda adolatli va muvozanatli shahar rejalashtirishiga yo'naltiradi.

Key words: urbanizatsiya, iqtisodiy barqarorlik, atrof-muhitga ta'sir, demografik tendensiyalar, ko'chmas mulk inqirozi, ortiqcha qurilish, O'zbekiston.

Аннотация: Урбанизация является основой экономического развития, но её быстрый и неконтролируемый характер может привести к серьёзным кризисам. Исследование, проведённое на примере Ташкента, описывает экономическую нестабильность, деградацию окружающей среды и демографическое давление, вызванное интенсивной урбанизацией, демонстрируя пример «городских социально-экономических проблем». Этот процесс приводит к искажениям на рынке жилья, увеличивает стоимость жизни, разрушает экологию и способствует неустойчивому росту населения в столице. Данное исследование, используя эмпирические данные и примеры, показывает последствия неконтролируемого роста городов. Эти выводы важны для обсуждения вопросов городской политики, так как помогают выявить ключевые стресс-факторы, а также дают рекомендации для сбалансированного и справедливого городского планирования, подчеркивая необходимость эффективного управления ресурсами и регулирования для предотвращения долгосрочных кризисов.

Ключевые слова: урбанизация, экономическая стабильность, воздействие на окружающую среду, демографические тенденции, кризис недвижимости, чрезмерное строительство, Узбекистан.

INTRODUCTION

Urbanization is the process of city growth and an increasing urban population, accompanied by infrastructure expansion, economic, and social changes. Urbanization as an important factor of economic development, can result in some socio-economic and environmental issues when it is not controlled properly. In Uzbekistan's capital Tashkent, all of these issues are compounded by fast urbanization that has led to overdevelopment of real estate features, enormous environmental pressure, and an ever-growing number of population. Urban growth presents ample opportunities in terms of infrastructure and a wide scope of trade-off towards economic well-being, yet its unregulated nature presents its own perils and incorporates market distortions and unnatural depletion of resources and ecological degradation.

One of the most important problems that accompany the intensive process of urbanization in Tashkent is the excessive construction of residential and commercial facilities. This phenomenon causes an unsustainable population density, exacerbating the pressure on public services and an increase in housing prices, making real estate no longer affordable for many citizens. Moreover, the failure to regulate these construction activities has led to severe environmental degradation, including deforestation, air pollution, and loss of green spaces, all of which adversely affect the overall quality of life in urban areas.

Data are collected through closed-ended survey questions and focused interview questions. It will examine how the real estate boom leads to financial imbalance urban congestion, and ecological harm. In addition, the research will analyze the implications of governmental policies regarding urban expansion and prevention of possible crisis. The attention will be focused to the statements and strategies of the President of Uzbekistan in terms of sustainable urban development, legislative activities that also aim for an adequate balance between development and environmental sustainability.

This study aims at adding to the current discussion of urban planning, and sustainable development in Uzbekistan, by exploring these factors. It will also help identify effective policy copy-paste strategies that can help balance urban growth, sustain economic growth, natural resource sustainability, and quality of urban living conditions.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

A recent review of journal articles and policy papers highlights increasing apprehension regarding the adverse effects of runaway urbanization. Despite the fact that urban growth is critical for economic development, it is often unregulated, leading to severe market imbalances, ecological degradation, and unsustainable infrastructure expansion, scholars argue. Research by UN-Habitat (2022)¹ and the World Bank Urban Development Series (2021)² found that speculative real estate booms, driven by fast-paced urban expansion, led to housing crises, inflated property values, and economic instability in different cities worldwide.

A quintessential problem of unregulated urbanization is speculation in land: an artificial speculation that prices up the market on behalf of speculators on the market and not on behalf of the citizens, where the latter, beyond price asymmetries, are the real losers. Glaeser et al. (2020)¹¹ disclose that cities encourage mobility and exacerbate socio-economic divides, for lower-income populations, this movement is often to the peripheries and urban inequality, and displacement becomes a by-product of this movement. That trend has been replicated in Beijing, which has seen an excessive amount of speculation in real estate leading to "ghost cities"—high-rise residential blocks that remain largely unoccupied due to overpriced housing. Li & Wu (2021)¹² provide additional evidence that speculative-led development often results in socially wasteful economic bubbles.

Apart from economic crisis, rapid urbanization comes with a huge strain on infrastructure and the environment. Unmitigated urban sprawl, according to Seto, Güneralp, & Hutyrá's (2012) research¹³, leads to irreversible loss of green areas everything that affects the effects of urbanization as well as heat and biodiversity loss Effects of urbanization on the environment / biodiversity & urban green spaces.

In addition, the urban governance literature highlights the need for policy intervention to mediate development and sustainability. As Rodríguez-Pose & Storper (2020)¹⁴ make clear, properly managed urban expansion (backed by appropriate zoning laws and environmental protection measures) can do much to alleviate the risk of overdevelopment. In Uzbekistan, the government's recent policy of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev's urban sustainability initiatives¹⁵— indicate increasing recognition of such challenges. But comparisons to countries such as Singapore and Germany show Uzbekistan still needs better regulations to continue growing sustainably.

Combining global knowledge with the case of Tashkent, this study embeds trends of urbanization in Uzbekistan into a wider dialogue of city planning for global sustainability, both contributing to and emerging through theory and policy efforts.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The PESTLE framework will be utilized in this study, which consists of Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Legal and Environmental elements of the rapid urbanization process in Tashkent. This angle assists in dissecting the ways in which government policy, market trends, social evolution, technological innovation, legal frameworks and environmental issues drive and govern the city's real estate boom and its fallout. To provide a comprehensive picture, the authors combine data analysis with examples from real life:

Uzbek government published reports and statistics related to urban development, construction permits and growth of population.

Real estate market (housing prices, speculative investments, volume of new construction).

Environmental research on air pollution, deforestation and water use from urban sprawl.

Comparative analysis of other cities grappling with comparable urbanization challenges. A notable case in point is China, whose breathtaking urbanization, especially in cities such as Beijing and Shenzhen, has ushered in speculative housing bubbles, ghost towns, and stark environmental destruction. The Chinese government's response – including tighter lending practices and urban planning reforms – provides important lessons for Uzbekistan.

To provide accuracy, trust and reliability:

Cross check on the data from multiple sources to remove bias.

The research process is transparent, with methods clearly documented.

The analysis focuses on long-term trends in urbanization to suggest future challenges.

The PESTLE approach used in this study gives a holistic view of what drives urban expansion in Tashkent, and how policies might be formulated differently at multiple structural levels in order to avoid economic instability and environmental degradation, especially where China serves as the key lesson learnt from.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Thousands of people are moving into Tashkent every month, triggered by ongoing and unregulated urbanization that has brought with it economic instability and demographic shifts, alongside environmental damage. Looking at these factors comparatively, with particular reference to China's real estate crisis 7, helps us understand the potential for risk and longer-term consequences. Defaults by groups of developers could have a destabilizing and cascading effect on the broader economy. Here, we offer a data-backed exploration, drawing from government reports, real estate market studies, and global urbanization trends to show the threats associated with too much construction.

1.Economic Consequences: Market Oversaturation and Economic Risk

Tashkent has become an influx of development, contributing to an overabundance of residential and commercial space. This unchecked expansion echoes China's Evergrande crisis, which saw runaway development, excess housing, plummeting prices and financial crisis (Table 1).

Table 1. Key Economic Indicators in Tashkent's Real Estate Market (2018-2023)

Year	New Residential Units Built	Average Price per m ² (\$)	Vacancy Rate (%)	Investment in Real Estate (billion \$)
2018	25,000	800	5%	2.1
2019	30,000	900	7%	2.8
2020	40,000	1,100	10%	3.5
2021	50,000	1,200	12%	4.2
2022	55,000	1,150	15%	4.5
2023	60,000	1,100	18%	4.1

The vacancy rate has almost quadrupled, indicating market saturation. Investors who viewed real estate once as a bedrock asset now find stagnating prices and capital losses, like the downturn when China's secondary cities deflated. The trend of falling investment inflows in 2023 indicates increasing investor wariness amid plummeting returns (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Vacancy Rate vs Real Estate Investment in Tashkent (2018-2023)

The potential collapse of a real estate bubble “could wreak havoc throughout Uzbekistan’s financial sector if developers depend excessively on credit financing, similar to the Chinese property behemoths”.

2.Environmental Effects: Deterioration of Green Areas and Pollution

The expansion of urban areas has resulted in deforestation, air pollution, and water resource pressure. A significant portion of CO₂ emissions comes from the construction sector, where poorly considered developments have taken over parks and green space with high-density housing and commercial zones.

Table 2. Environmental Decline in Tashkent (2013–2023)

Year	Green Space per Capita (m ²)	Air Pollution (PM2.5, µg/m ³)	Water Consumption (million m ³ /year)
2013	12.5	35	250
2018	9.8	48	320
2023	6.4	65	400

Tashkent is facing severe environmental issues due to rapid urbanization. One such problem is deforestation, and the rise of urban heat islands, with green space per capita declining nearly 50% in the last decade. This loss has contributed to increased temperatures, especially in the city center, amplifying the extremes of urban living conditions. Air quality has deteriorated as well; PM2.5 pollution levels, surpassing WHO safety limits and causing major health problems. But water scarcity has also been on the rise, with increased demand in newly constructed urban districts straining existing reservoirs. Such a situation mirrors Beijing’s perpetual urban water crisis, where rapid growth has outstripped available water resources, causing long-term sustainability crises for residents in the city (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Reduction in Green Space vs Increase in Air Pollution in Tashkent (2013-2023)

In the absence of sustainable urban planning, Tashkent faces dire environmental challenges, ranging from climate-induced migration to elevated health risks for its citizens.

3. Population Growth, Demographics and Related Infrastructure Stress

The economic center of Uzbekistan, Tashkent has seen heavy migration from rural areas, creating pressure on infrastructure, housing and public services (Table 3).

Table 3. Urban Population Growth vs. Infrastructure Development in Tashkent (2018-2023)

Year	Population (millions)	Public Transport Capacity (millions/day)	Affordable Housing Demand (units)
2018	2.5	1.2	15,000
2019	2.7	1.3	18,000
2020	2.9	1.4	22,000
2021	3.1	1.5	27,000
2022	3.4	1.6	33,000
2023	3.6	1.7	38,000

Most people, cannot afford to rent one, while low-income families struggle to find any kind of housing at all, creating a gap between Kent’s new luxury apartments and a growing number of people without shelter. Traffic jams are another pain point, with the city’s transport infrastructure, which was built for 1.7 million daily commuters, buckling under a population of 3.6 million. This leads to longer commutes and increased vehicle emissions, which contribute to air pollution. Moreover, public services including schools, hospitals and utilities are stretched to breaking point, struggling to cope with the city’s growing population. Similar to the urban stress suffered by many megacities of rapid growth in places like Beijing and Istanbul, this poses an important challenge as maturing areas, especially those that are so densely packed, will ultimately require sustainable solutions as development meets its limits (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Population Growth vs Transport and Housing Development in Tashkent.

Without control, this unregulated population growth is likely to result in social disparity, degrading quality of life and living standards in urban areas.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

The results of this research demonstrate that adequate and uncontrolled urbanization in Tashkent has caused substantial problems in terms of economy, ecology and demography. An intensive speculative investment driven demand, and congestion of the sector has led to asset price fluctuations and an increasing number of empty buildings. It resembles trends seen in cities such as Beijing, where construction has outstripped its economic risks.

The economic repercussions are not the only burden we have to bear from urban expansion: the natural environment of Tashkent have faced immense pressure with deforestation, loss of green belts, and increasing pollution. The deteriorating air quality and excessive consumption of resources are evidence of the ecological price of rampant development.

The fragility of the city's own infrastructure is unsustainable as it tries to keep pace with a burgeoning population, resulting in scarcity of affordable housing, overcrowded transportation systems, and a transactional public services sector. These problems are compounded by an influx of people into the capital, raising long-term sustainability issues.

Ultimately, the research shows that untrammled urbanization, often viewed as a marker of economic progress, can create entrenched vulnerabilities. Tashkent's future development will need to keep this balance of growth vs sustainability vs livability – it will take an active effort to achieve.

List of used literature

1. UN-Habitat (2022) - World Cities Report 2022 https://unhabitat.org/sites/default/files/2022/06/wcr_2022.pdf
2. World Bank Urban Development Overview <https://www.worldbank.org/en/topic/urbandevelopment/overview>
3. Speculative Behavior in a Housing Market: Boom and Bust <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0264999316307568>
4. Speculative Culture and Corporate High-Quality Development in China <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41599-024-03404-8>
5. Global Forecasts of Urban Expansion to 2030 and Direct Impacts on Biodiversity and Carbon Pools <https://www.pnas.org/doi/10.1073/pnas.1211658109>
6. Housing, Urban Growth, and Inequalities: The Limits to Deregulation and Upzoning in Reducing Economic and Spatial Inequality <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.1177/0042098019859458>
7. China's Housing Booms: A Challenge to Bubble Theory <https://shs.hal.science/halshs-02963810/document>
8. Urban Inequality https://scholar.harvard.edu/files/glaeser/files/urban_inequality.pdf

9. Global Impacts of Future Urban Expansion on Terrestrial Vertebrate Biodiversity <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41467-022-29324-2>
10. Overcoming Left-Behindness: Moving Beyond the Efficiency Versus Equity Conundrum <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S175778022400355X>
11. Glaeser et al. (2020) research <https://awionline.org/lab-animal-search/glaeser-s-s-edwards-k-l-wielebnowski-n-et-al-2020-effects-physiological-changes>
12. Li & Wu (2021) research <https://essuir.sumdu.edu.ua/handle/123456789/93834>
13. Seto, Güneralp, & Hutyra's (2012) research <https://www.scirp.org/reference/referencespapers?referenceid=2787624>
14. Rodríguez-Pose & Storper (2020) research <https://ideas.repec.org/a/sae/urbstu/v57y2020i2p223-248.html>
15. President Shavkat Mirziyoev's urban sustainability initiatives <https://www.reuters.com/sustainability/climate-energy/uzbekistan-announces-13-blm-waste-to-energy-projects-2024-10-21/>
16. Key Economic Indicators in Tashkent's Real Estate Market (2018-2023) <https://www.spot.uz/ru/2024/01/22/real-estate-2023/>
17. Environmental Decline in Tashkent (2013–2023) <https://vaib.uz/2024/01/21/strashnye-czifry-vsego-za-shest-let-rastitelnost-v-tashkente-sokratilas-s-346-do-131/> and <https://uz.sputniknews.ru/20231129/uzbekistan-derevyavyrubka-sokrascheniye-41312133.html>
18. Urban Population Growth vs. Infrastructure Development in Tashkent (2018-2023) <https://www.gazeta.uz/ru/2023/12/07/cmwp/>

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Oloviddin Sobir o'g'li

2025. № 4

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelmasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

Mazkur jurnalda maqolalar chop etish uchun quyidagi havolalarga maqola, reklama, hikoya va boshqa ijodiy materiallar yuborishingiz mumkin. Materiallar va reklamalar pullik asosda chop etiladi.

EI.Pochta: sq143235@gmail.com

Bot: @iqtisodiyot_77

Tel.: 93 718 40 07

Jurnalga istalgan payt quyidagi rekvizitlar orqali obuna bo'lishingiz mumkin. Obuna bo'lgach, @iqtisodiyot_77 telegram sahifamizga to'lov haqidagi ma'lumotni skrinshot yoki foto shaklida jo'natishingizni so'raymiz. Shu asosda har oygi jurnal yangi sonini manzilingizga jo'natamiz.

"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>